

EFFICIENCY OF GAMIFICATION IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract: Since gamification has been shown in studies to boost student engagement, more and more teachers are incorporating game elements into their lessons. A lot of people have expressed optimism about the widespread use of gamification, which has gained popularity as an educational tool. This article is devoted analysing the gamification process from the viewpoints of young children' academic achievement and inspiration to learn.

Key words: e-learning experience, goal-oriented learning, gamified education, digital literacy.

INGLIZ TILINI O'RGANISHDA GAMIFIKATSIYANING SAMARADORLIGI

Gamifikatsiya usulidan foydalanib, o`quvchining faolligini oshirish maqsadida ko`proq o`qituvchilar hozirgi kunda ba`zi o'yin elementlarini o'z ichiga olgan interaktiv darslarni tashkil etishmoqdahamda ko`p odamlar ta`lim vositasi sifatida mashhurlikka erishgan gamifikatsiyaning keng qo`llanilishi va uning natijalari haqida ijobiy fikrlar bildirishmoqda. Ushbu maqolada gamifikatsiya metodining yosh til o`rganuvchilarning til o`rganish jarayonidagi yutuqlari erishishida bo`lgan roli va hissasi haqida so`z boradi.

**Kalit so`zlar:** elektron ta`lim tajribasi, maqsadga yo`naltirilgan ta`lim, gamifikatsiyalangan ta`lim, raqamli savodxonlik.

ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ГЕЙМИФИКАЦИИ ПРИ ИЗУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация: Поскольку исследования показали, что геймификация повышает вовлеченность учащихся, все больше и больше учителей включают игровые элементы в свои уроки. Многие люди с оптимизмом смотрят на широкое использование геймификации, которая приобрела популярность в качестве образовательного инструмента. Эта статья посвящена анализу процесса

геймификации с точки зрения академических достижений маленьких детей и их стремления учиться.

Ключевые слова: опыт электронного обучения, целенаправленное обучение, игровое образование, цифровая грамотность.

In the study of foreign languages, gamification is becoming more and more common. Gamification is a technique that engages people and helps them have fun in computer-mediated and non-gaming contexts while empowering their motives (Seaborn & Fels, 2015). Gamification is a concept that includes non-gaming environment, methodical and artistic game designs, and game features (badges, points, awards, etc.). Its goal aims are not limited to just enjoyment or entertainment. Both of them participate in the educational process as pupils play games. Through the use of language games, students can effectively acquire the target language in a relaxed setting. Gamification may also encourage students to practice their learning, and pupils benefit from playing games in the classroom (Barab et al., 2009). It can be used by people of almost any age or language proficiency. Pupils may develop their literacy, critical thinking, speaking, listening, digital literacy, and problem-solving abilities, among other 21st-century competencies. Since students can make corrections on their own without undue stress, learner autonomy rises. By learning at their own speed, they advance (Maloney, 2019). Meaningful communication that digital games foster in foreign language instruction helps students participate more successfully by laying the groundwork for meaningful inputs. Since review studies on English learning using games have been conducted at the primary and higher education levels, there hasn't been one on the secondary school level, where students in various countries range in age from 11 to 18. According to the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED, 2011), secondary education is divided into two categories: ISCED 2 (lower secondary school) for students aged 12 to 15 and ISCED 3 (upper secondary school) for those aged 15 to 18. For English learning to be reinforced and elaborated, this time frame is essential. The studies of participants aged 11 to 18 were selected as secondary school age ranges for this review study in order to prevent data loss due to age. Students should learn English for research purposes as secondary schools prepare them for higher education.

Gamification is not the same as simulations that replicate real-world teaching environments or games that are primarily created for enjoyment. Gamified education just makes use of gaming components to boost student involvement and enthusiasm to acquire new skills. The lack of student enthusiasm to participate in class is a major issue in English instruction. The content analysis makes clear that the participants' regular use of coin collecting to address the reward system was prevalent. Because students can only obtain prizes for successfully completing each assignment, it fosters

goal-oriented learning. But for today's students, this is not surprising. Students are now accustomed to item collecting from a variety of role-playing games (RPG) or strategy games, like Defense of the Ancients (DOTA), Resident Evil, and Final Fantasy, to mention a few, thanks to the increasing popularity of online gaming. These games are similar in that they allow players to accumulate uncommon goods or collector coins, which they may then trade in for more infrequent stuff or helpful gadgets when they play them again. Additionally, teachers should strike a balance between integrating these technologies and students' capacities to profit from the incorporation of game-play in English learning, especially the many advantages of implementing gamification in school or education settings. All things considered, making sure the game is fit can assist game designers in avoiding these problems and ensure that the game enhances the learning experiences of the students while motivating and encouraging English learning at various phases.

In conclusion, using gamification in e-learning can help teachers provide their students completely interesting learning experiences. They remain motivated and engaged since they are working towards a goal thanks to gamification. Even though you may have several learning objectives and goals for your eLearning course, none of them will be accomplished if the students aren't engaged with the material. Gamification in eLearning brings excitement and pleasure to learning in addition to information. Students can see the practical applications and advantages of the subject matter through gamification in e-learning. They are able to observe directly how the decisions they make in the game impact the outcomes or benefits they obtain. Whether you are creating eLearning outputs for adult learners or younger pupils, gamification can substantially improve the effectiveness of the entire eLearning experience. If students are enjoying themselves and becoming enthusiastic about studying, they are more likely to actually retain the material. Because students are engaged in the process and enjoying it, even dull or challenging material can be assimilated more readily.

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